

Quercetin Metabolism and Transport Dynamics in the Presence of Benzo(a)pyrene: An In Vitro Investigation

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ABSTRACT

Quercetin is a flavonoid able to modify the metabolism of carcinogen benzo(a)pyrene in human intestinal cells but it is not known if its metabolism is affected by the presence of B(a)P. In this study the phase-2 metabolism and transport rate of quercetin has been studied using CaCo-2/TC7 cell line, model of human enterocytes, co-treated with B(a)P. Quercetin and its main metabolites, sulfated and glucuronidated, were quantified at different times (from T0 to T 24h), using HPLC with diode array and MS detection. This study showed that quercetin metabolism in CaCo-2/TC7 cells co-treated with B(a)P presents some differences respect to control in the formation of sulphates conjugates, more evident in the last time of analysis. The transport study, instead, confirmed a stronger influence of BaP with an increased rate of glucuronidation and sulfation of quercetin in both cellular side. The effects of B(a)P observed on phase-2 metabolism and transport rate of quercetin, by *in vitro* model of human enterocytes, put in evidence its possible influence, consequently, also on biological activities of this flavonoid.

Keywords: Benzo(a)pyrene, quercetin, CaCo-2 cell line, metabolism, transport, HPLC-MS.

INTRODUCTION

Diet represents a significant source of exposure to contaminants and food-borne carcinogens as benzo(a)pyrene but, at the same time, a font of assumption of phytochemicals, as quercetin, with protective effects for human health. Many studies showed a correlation between high dietary intake of cooked meat and an increased risk of cancer of colon, pancreas, liver, prostate and breast¹ due to the presence of food-borne cancerogens and mutagens.

Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) is a marker of cancerogenicity of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), produced during cooking processes (drying, boiling, cooking, grilling, roasting, toasting, smoking)²⁻³ for combustion of organic matter. Due to their physical and chemical properties, BaP has an high solubility in lipids, can migrate through the food chain into hydrophobic compartments and be retained by food rich in fats⁴⁻⁶. At the same time, it could be present in food as consequence of environmental pollution⁷, in fact substantial amounts of this toxic compound were found also in vegetable foods (bread, cereals, grains, fruits, etc.)⁸⁻⁹.

Epidemiological studies, instead, have shown that diets rich in fruit and vegetables are associated with a lower risk of developing food-related malignancies¹⁰⁻¹¹, for the presence of phytochemical compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids, antocyanidines, isotyocyanates ect.), considered natural anti-carcinogens¹²⁻¹⁴. Among these phytochemicals, quercetin is a major flavonoid present in

various fruits (as blackberry, mulberry, apple, etc.) and vegetables (as onion, broccoli, etc.), with a wide range of *in vitro* biological activities¹⁵, such as antinflammatory, antioxidant anticancer, antidiabetic, etc.¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Therefore, at present, there is an increasing interest to assess the fate of food contaminants and phytochemical compounds after food ingestion and their possible interactions in the gastrointestinal tract. Particularly, the CaCo-2 cell line, is widely used as a model to study human intestinal transport and metabolism, biotransformation and permeability¹⁹. The CaCo-2 cell line, established from a human colon adenocarcinoma, has retained the ability to differentiate into polarized epithelial monolayers, shows numerous biochemical and morphological characteristics of enterocytes (e.g., formation of microvilli, tight junctions and desmosomes, expression of brush-border enzymes such as sucraseisomaltase)²⁰ and expresses various phase-1 and phase-2 enzymes. In particular, the CaCo-2 sub-clone TC7, generated by passaging CaCo-2 cells 198 times²¹, is characterized by a selection of faster growing cells, shorter population doubling time, higher cell density and full differentiation after a shorter period of time, in respect to the parent population.

The absorption and metabolism of many bioactive compounds, like quercetin, has been studied in CaCo-2 cell line²²⁻²³. Quercetin aglycone is initially absorbed in gastrointestinal tract by passive diffusion²⁴⁻²⁵, then hydrolyzed and further conjugated within the enterocytes

Figure 1: Chromatographic profile of quercetin and its main metabolites in co-treatment with B(a)P.

1. quercetin-7-glucuronide (Q-7-GlcA); 2. quercetin-3'-glucuronide (Q-3'-GlcA); 3. 3'-methylquercetin-3-glucuronide (IR-3-GlcA); 4. quercetin-4'-glucuronide (Q-4'-GlcA); 5. quercetin-3-glucuronide (Q-3-GlcA); 6. quercetin (Q); 7. quercetin-3-sulphate (Q-3-S); 8. benzo(a)pyrene B(a)P

by enzymes, to form a number of phase-2 conjugates, most notably sulphates and glucuronides²⁶⁻²⁸. Finally quercetin conjugates are excreted by the liver, reducing their bioavailability.

Similarly, BaP transport²⁹⁻³⁰, uptake and metabolism³¹ have been investigated in CaCo-2 cell line³²⁻³³. Some authors have studied the effects of polyphenols and flavonoids³⁴⁻³⁵, like ellagic acid³⁶ and chrysin³⁷, on metabolic activation¹³, cellular excretion³⁸ and transport³⁹ of benzo(a)pyrene but no data are reported on influence of this carcinogen on metabolic behaviour of phytochemical compounds as quercetin. The aim of this study, therefore, is to evaluate the effects of BaP on phase 2-metabolism of flavonoid quercetin and its cellular transport rate in CaCo-2 cell line, co-exposed to this toxic compound.

MATERIALS and METHODS

CaCo-2/TC7 cell culture

The clonal line CaCo-2/TC7, derived from parental CaCo-2 cells, obtained from Dr Monique Rousset (INSERM, Paris, France), were cultured between passages 32 and 51. Cells were grown in Dulbecco Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) with 1% nonessential amino acids, 1% L-glutamine, 100 IU/ML penicillin and 100 µg/ml

streptomycin, supplemented with 20% (v/v) foetal calf serum (FCS). At first, cells were sub-cultured 5-6 days post seeding. Cell were seeded at $2-4 \times 10^4$ cells in 75 cm² flask and sub-cultured 5-6 days post seeding when the cells reached 80% confluency observed under a light microscope. Finally, cells were seeded at $2-4 \times 10^4$ cells per cm² on 10 cm dishes (growing area 75 cm²) and allowed to grow until 21 days post confluent, changing media 3 daily. *Chemicals*

Quercetin standard solution was purchased from Extrasynthese, 69727 Genay Cedex, France. Quercetin-3glucuronide (Q3glA), quercetin-3'-glucuronide (Q3'glA), quercetin-4-glucuronide (Q4glA), quercetin-7glucuronide (Q7glA), and 3-methylquercetin-3glucuronide (isorhamnetin-3-glucuronide, IR3glA) were chemically synthesized at the Institute of Food Research,

Figure 2: Quercetin’s metabolites rate, in presence of benzo(a)pyrene (BaP cot), expressed as a) total glucuronides (TOT GLcA), b) total sulphates (TOT Sulphates) and c) total conjugates (TOT Coniugates). * $P < 0.05$

Norwich³⁹ while quercetin 7-sulphate was provided by Dr Denis Barron, Nestle ResearchCentre, Lausanne, Switzerland. Purity of compounds was checked by HPLC with UV detection and was 98.5% for all. Benzo(a)pyrene standard solutions, all solvents and other reagents of analytical grade were obtained from Sigma– Aldrich, Poole, UK.

Metabolism studies

Cells were treated, in triplicate, with solution of quercetin (60 μM) as control, co-treated with quercetin (60 μM) and benzo(a)pyrene (10 μM) and DMSO was used as analytical blank. After incubation, aliquots of extracellular culture samples at different times (T 0, 30 min, 1h, 2h, 4h, 8h and 24h) were collected and treated with 20 μl of Acetonitrile and Formic Acid, stored at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, centrifuged and transferred in vials for chromatographic analysis²².

A stability study of quercetin in presence of BaP was also carried out in fresh and spent media (after 2h of incubation); media samples, collected at different times of incubation (T 0, 2h, 4h and 8h), were treated in the same conditions previously described.

Preparation of CaCo-2/TC7 monolayers for transport studies

A CaCo-2/TC7 monolayer was prepared by seeding cells (from 75 cm² flasks) at 2-4 x 10⁴ cells per cm² on 12 – well of 0.65 μm (0.33 cm²) Transwell polycarbonate filters (Corning Costar Corporation, Sigma- Aldrich, UK) and grown to confluence for 21 days. The media was changed every 2 days and cells were allowed to grow until 21 days

before and at the end of experiments to ensure adequate monolayer integrity.

Transport studies

From apical and basolateral compartments of CaCo2/TC7 monolayer, the media was removed by aspiration and 0.2 ml and 1 ml of samples were added in apical and basolateral side, respectively. To study quercetin transport in co-treatment with BaP, in Transwell system of 0.65 μm (0.33

Table 1: Metabolic behaviour of quercetin (60 μM) in cotreatment with benzo(a)pyrene (10 μM).

	Q-7-GlcA	Q GlcA	-3'- IR GlcA	Q-3-	Q-4'- GlcA	Q-3 -GlcA	QUERCET IN	Q-3'- S	
T 0	conc μM								
QUE (control)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	60.635 ± 11.72	n.d.	
QUER (BaP ct)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	60.184 ± 10.84	n.d.	
T 1h	conc μM								
QUE (control)	0.806 ±0.45	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.981 ± 0.040	45.58 ± 7.24	2.259 ± 0.831	
QUER (BaP ct)	0.939 ±0.26	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.821 ± 0.088	40.894 ± 8.67	1.639 ± 0.584	
T 2h	conc μM								
QUE (control)	4.413 ± 0.50	0.415 ± 0.079	0.253 ± 0.027	0.431 ± 0.017	3.221 ± 0.583	33.971 ± 3.464	4.063 ± 0.556		
QUER (BaP ct)	5.297 ± 1.211	0.670 ±0.194	0.202 ± 0.016	0.280 ± 0.045	2.399 ± 0.143	30.711 ±6.424	2.857 ± 0.853**		
T 4h	conc μM								
QUE (control)	10.562± 1.51	1.107 ± 0.24	0.591 ± 0.036	1.316 ± 0.322	8.914 ± 0.997	15.851 ± 2.682	11.239 ± 0.765		
QUER (BaP ct)	12.084 ±2.185*	1.068 ± 0.113	0.542 ± 0.045	1.187 ± 0.074	8.283 ±1.051	9.062 ±1.091**	11.520 ±2.722		
T 8h	conc μM								
QUE (control)	16.558 ±4.438	3.205 ± 0.581	1.499 ±0.349	3.439 ±0.508	19.001 ±4.793	0.217 ±0.029	15.528 ±1.318		
QUER (BaP ct)	15.189 ±3.919	2.490 ±0.373*	1.738 ±0.137	3.635 ±0.757	15.309 ±3.139**	0.186 ±0.041*	18.116 ±1.645**		
T 24h	conc μM								
QUE (control)	17.945±0.9	3.378 ±0.660	2.112 ±0.437	4.413 ±0.816	21.089 ±1.244	n.d	17.225±0.68		
QUER (BaP ct)	91 ±2.055	2.719 ±0.472	2.107 ±0.088	4.412 ±0.808	19.938 ±3.260*	n.d	6 ± 18.543±2.69		

post confluent. The evaluation of monolayer *P<0.05**P<0.01

integrity of the cells in the Transwells was determined by measuring transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) using a Millicell-ERS volt ohmmeter (Millipore corporation, Billerica, Massachusetts, USA)⁴⁰. TEER measurements of 6 and 12 well Transwells monolayers were routinely made prior to changing the cell culture media; additionally TEER measurements were taken also

cm²), cells were treated, in both apical and basolateral side, in triplicate, with solution of quercetin (60μM) used as control, co-treated with quercetin (60μM) and benzo(a)pyrene (10 μM), while DMSO was used like analytical blank. Aliquots collected at different time after incubation (T 0, 15min, 1h, 2h, 4h, 8h and 24h) were treated with 20μl of Acetonitrile and Formic Acid and analyzed as previously described. *Determination of apical to basolateral ratio from transport experiments*

To calculate the amount (μM) of flavonoids (aglycone and all metabolites) in the apical and basolateral side, the peak

area from the HPLC chromatograms was considered. The apical to basolateral ratio is expressed by the equation below: $\text{ratio} = \frac{\text{apical efflux}}{\text{basolateral efflux}}$

This ratio is a measure of the favoured direction of efflux, where value of over 1.0 indicating an apically favoured efflux, values below 1.0 symbolising a basolaterally favoured efflux, and values of 1.0 symbolising an equal distribution of conjugate efflux.

HPLC analysis

The study of quercetin metabolism was realized in an Agilent 1100 HPLC (Agilent, Stockport, UK) comprising of two pump units, auto-sampler, mixer, and a diodearray detector at λ_{max} 270 and 370 nm, using a Phenomenex Luna C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm i.d.) 5 μm equipped with guard column. Samples were eluted using like mobile phase MilliQ water (A) and Acetonitrile (B) with 0.1% TFA, at this elution gradient: 17% (B) from 0 to 2 min ; 25% B from 2 to 7 min; 35% B from 7 to 15 min; 50% from 15 to 20 ; 100% B from 20 to 25 min; 100% B until 30 min; 17% B from 30 to 35 min, followed until 50 min. Analysis was conducted at

To validate the chromatographic method used, all specific parameters were assessed. The limit of detection (LOD) for quercetin and its metabolites was determined as 0.007 μM . To check the linearity, standard solution of quercetin and its metabolites at different concentrations (40, 20, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were analysed. Calibration curves for each compound were constructed using the linear least-squares regression procedure ($n=4$) of peak area versus standard concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ($R^2=0.999$). The accuracy and repeatability of the method was assessed by performing a spike-and-recovery test. Recovery was measured using fortified samples ($n = 3$ replicates) each at three levels of concentration, corresponding to 85 %, 100% and 110%, respectively, for each analyte. Spike recoveries were repeated three times for each concentrations and the results were expressed as average percentage of recovery. The specificity was confirmed by analysis of blank samples. To confirm quercetin metabolites detection by HPLC, further analysis were performed using LC with mass spectrometry in positive mode (Micromass Quattro II; Manchester, UK)²². Chromatographic runs were carried out

Figure 3: Quercetin stability test in fresh (a) and spent (b) media in presence of B(a)P.

temperature of 20 C°, at flow of 1 ml/min and injection volume was 50 μl .

under the same conditions previously described. The limit of detection in culture media samples was determined as 0.004 μM .

Statistical analysis

The results were reported as mean value ± S.D. from a minimum of three replicate measurements. When total conjugates, glucuronates (GlcA) and sulphates are reported, the data were obtained by summing all the values for the individual conjugates but did not include the free quercetin. Data were submitted to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and paired sample *t*-test to determine the significance of differences between groups. P values <0.01 and <0.05 were accepted as statistically significant.

RESULTS

Metabolism studies

The metabolic profile of quercetin and its main metabolites (quercetin-7- glucuronide, quercetin 3'- glucuronide, IR-quercetin 3- glucuronide, quercetin 3- glucuronide, quercetin 4'- glucuronide, quercetin 3- sulphate), identified and quantified in co-treatment with Benzo(a)pyrene through the chromatographic analysis, is reported in Figure 1.

The concentrations of quercetin and its metabolites in cells co-treated with BaP at different times, in comparison to the control, are reported in Table 1. In

Figure 4: Comparison between quercetin’s transport rate, in apical and basolateral directions, in the presence of benzo(a)pyrene, expressed as total GlcA (a), total Sulphate (b), to

particular, from these data it’s possible to observe that quercetin decreases significantly at 4h (P<0.01), respect to control, until to be absent at 24h (considered the last step of metabolic process). All main metabolites of quercetin are present after 2h; their concentrations present same differences (P<0.05 and P<0.01) in presence of BaP during the intermediate time of analysis (4h and 8h), reacting at

24h values lower than control, except for Q-7GlcA and Q-3'-S. These results were expressed also in Figure 2 as sum of glucuronates metabolites (Tot GlcA), sulphate metabolites (Tot Sulphates) and total conjugates (Tot conjugates), except free quercetin. In presence of BaP the production of glucuronates metabolites is similar to control until 4h but decreases significantly from 8 h to

to control at 4h but decreases from 8 h until to the last metabolic step at 24h.

In Figure 3 is reported the study of quercetin stability in presence of BaP, in fresh and spent media (after 2h of incubation). The results obtained showed a similar trend in both experimental conditions, with a gradual loss of quercetin from 1h to 8h in fresh media (Fig 3a), more in co-treatment with benzo(a)pyrene.

Table 2: Transport rate (conc μM) of quercetin in apical side.

T 0	QUERCETIN <i>conc μM</i>	TOT GlcA	TOT Sulphate	TOT Conjugates
QUE (control)	59.94 \pm 9.324	-	-	-
QUER (BaP ct)	59.79 \pm 8.187	-	-	-
T 30 min	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	53.36 \pm 7.328	0.132 \pm 0.065	4.362 \pm 0.837	4.494 \pm 0.921
QUER (BaP ct)	52.499 \pm 5.492	-	6.242 \pm 1.328	6.242 \pm 1.538
T 1 h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	49.06 \pm 5.033	0.788 \pm 0.033	6.839 \pm 1.243	8.331 \pm 1.738
QUER (BaP ct)	49.064 \pm 7.257	0.355 \pm 0.048	6.839 \pm 1.025	7.529 \pm 0.937
T 2h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	22.67 \pm 3.176	1.823 \pm 0.656	5.332 \pm 0.963	7.727 \pm 1.533
QUER (BaP ct)	17.473 \pm 4.226*	1.528 \pm 0.092	20.215 \pm 1.985**	22.242 \pm 4.281**
T 4h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	4.477 \pm 0.983	3.044 \pm 0.927	7.009 \pm 1.052	10.481 \pm 1.772
QUER (BaP ct)	7.174 \pm 2.117	2.758 \pm 0.671	9.307 \pm 1.143	12.281 \pm 2.004
T 8h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	0.425 \pm 0.084	2.328 \pm 0.821	6.631 \pm 0.972	10.349 \pm 1.637
QUER (BaP ct)	0.184 \pm 0.028	2.735 \pm 0.573	7.800 \pm 1.297	11.376 \pm 2.148

* $P < 0.05$

** $P < 0.01$

Figure 5: Quercetin transport rate, in co-treatment with benzo(a)pyrene, expressed as Apical/Basolateral ratio of total conjugates. * $P < 0.05$

24h, respect to control (Fig 2a), instead, the rate of sulphates metabolites is higher than control from 8h to 24h (Fig 2b). Considering the total production of phase 2 metabolites (Fig 2c), it's possible to observe that in presence of BaP the total amount of conjugates is similar

evident at 4h and 8h in "spent" media (Fig. 3b), possible due to the slow auto-oxidation of quercetin in media.

Transport studies

Data related to the transport of quercetin and its metabolites in apical and basolateral side of cells, in presence of BaP, are reported in Table 2 and 3, respectively. In apical side, quercetin concentrations in

cells co-treated with BaP decreased respect to control, except to 4h; the total glucuronates content is less than control, but the sulphates are increased for all time of analysis with a maximum value at t 2h, with statistically significant differences (Table 2). In basolateral side, the content of quercetin decreased significantly in cells cotreated with BaP, in all time of analysis; the rate of glucuronidation and sulfation of quercetin is increased respect to control, reacting the maximum values at 2h ($P < 0.01$), then both decreased significantly in the last metabolic steps (Table 3). From a comparative analysis of quercetin transport rate in presence of BaP in both cellular compartments (Fig.4) it's possible to observe an increase of glucuronidation rate for each time of analysis but with higher concentrations basolateral than in apical side (Fig 4a). Instead, the sulphatation rate increased in both cellular side until to 2h, with higher concentrations in basolateral than apical sides, and then decreased (Fig

DISCUSSION

To assess the fate of food contaminants and phytochemical compounds when they reach the intestinal epithelial cells is very important because their interaction at level of this first barrier either allows or prevents their entry in the gut³⁴ and, consequently, could influence their toxic and biological effects. In literature several authors report the impact of quercetin and other polyphenols on BaP⁴¹, its toxic activities⁴²⁻⁴⁴, metabolism and enzymatic induction⁴⁵⁻⁴⁶. This study, on the contrary, describing the *in vitro* effects of BaP on phase-2 metabolism and transport rate of quercetin confirms that the co-treatment with BaP is able to influence quercetin metabolism, inducing the activity of phase-2 enzyme. Particularly an evident reduction of glucuronidation of quercetin (by *UDP-glucuronosyl transferases*) has been observed in the last time of analysis (from 8h to 24h), while the

Table 3: Quercetin transport rate (conc μ M) in basolateral side, in co-treatment with benzo(a)pyrene.

	QUERCETIN	TOT GlcA	TOT Sulphate	TOT Conjugates
T 0	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	59.99 \pm 8.372	-	-	-
QUER (BaP ct)	59.92 \pm 9.817	-	-	-
T 30 min	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	58.422 \pm 7.281	0.238 \pm 0.032	9.170 \pm 1.734	9.409 \pm 1.492
QUER (BaP ct)	53.561 \pm 8.841	-	11.109 \pm 2.341	11.109 \pm 2.107
T 1 h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	51.963 \pm 5.385	0.477 \pm 0.054	11.593 \pm 1.586	12.363 \pm 2.218
QUER (BaP ct)	45.416 \pm 8.431	0.973 \pm 0.061	12.922 \pm 2.073	14.186 \pm 2.719
T 2h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	31.793 \pm 4.387	1.397 \pm 0.657	13.732 \pm 2.528	15.469 \pm 2.781
QUER (BaP ct)	24.012 \pm 5.103**	4.997 \pm 1.052**	22.542 \pm 3.548**	28.053 \pm 3.006**
T 4h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	18.527 \pm 2.527	5.858 \pm 1.341	18.863 \pm 4.381	25.327 \pm 3.718
QUER (BaP ct)	8.951** \pm 1.928	4.267 \pm 0.548	14.229 \pm 3.205	18.774 \pm 2.711
T 8h	<i>conc μM</i>			
QUE (control)	2.574 \pm 0.822	8.123 \pm 1.945	17.237 \pm 2.337	25.706 \pm 3.106
QUER (BaP ct)	0.255 \pm 0.051**	4.699 \pm 0.856*	12.798* \pm 1.045	17.713 \pm 1.347

4b). Considering the total conjugates, it showed a similar $*P < 0.05$ $**P < 0.01$

behaviour in both cellular side: metabolites reacted the highest value at 2h (Fig 4c), considered the maximum metabolic step to possible effects of BaP on phase-2 enzyme, and then decreased slowly until to 8h. The effects of this co-treatment with BaP were evaluated on the AP:BL efflux ratio, using only quercetin conjugates for the calculation (Fig 5). Quercetin transport rate in presence of BaP was similar to control until 1h and higher from 2h until to 8h, with differences statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). This ratio AP/BL was < 1 in all time, showing a basolaterally favoured efflux.

sulphatation is increased (by *sulfotransferases*) in the last metabolic rates, in comparison with control. To better understand data obtained, further investigations were carried out to evaluate a possible influence of BaP on quercetin stability but no significant effects were observed in all different experimental conditions of analysis. In fact, the stability of quercetin, analyzed in fresh and spent media, appeared moderately reduced in presence of BaP, respect to control, for all times of analysis. However, in both experimental conditions have to be considered also the slow process of auto-oxidation of quercetin in media. As largely documented by other authors⁴⁷, in cell culture the flavonoids decrease intracellular production of reactive oxygen species but, at the same time, may produce them in the extracellular medium, leading to

disorder of redox homeostasis, cellular signaling, transcriptional factors and gene expression^{48-49,47}.

The transport represents a critical step able to influence the adsorption and metabolism of antioxidants as quercetin and, clearly, the carcinogen BaP is a key factor in the whole process. In fact, the studies carried out in apical and basolateral side of Caco-2 cells, during cotreatment with BaP, showed a clear influence of this toxic compound on transport rate of quercetin and its metabolites. The effect of BaP on transfer rate of quercetin metabolites in both cellular side, with a ratio AP/BL <1 in all time, demonstrated a basolaterally favoured efflux and this is of interest because could favourer also on absorption of this flavonoid.

The increased rate of both glucuronidation and sulfation in apical and basolateral side in presence of BaP could be due to a possible enhancement of proteins transfer or to induction of multi-drug resistance protein transporters^{50,51}, responsible of absorption or excretion of quercetin and its metabolites.

In conclusion, this *in vitro* study showed for the first time that carcinogen B(a)P induced significant changes in phase-2 metabolism and transport rate of the flavonoid quercetin by Caco-2 cells, model of human enterocytes. The influence of BaP on quercetin metabolism and transport rate puts in evidence a possible effect of this toxic compounds as enzymatic inductor of phase-2 enzyme (UDP-GT and ST), probably for their enhancement of enzymatic activities, with significant effects on quercetin bioavailability. However, further investigations are needed to better understand this effects and clarify the real role of BaP on kinetic behaviour of quercetin and, consequently on its biological effects for human health.

REFERENCES

1. Kapiszewska, M. A vegetable to meat consumption ratio as a relevant factor determining cancer preventive diet. The Mediterranean versus other European countries. *Forum Nutrition* 2006; 59: 13053.
2. Codex Alimentarius Commission (CX/FAC 06/38/36) 2005. Joint FAO/WHO food standards programme codex committee on food additives and contaminants. Discussion paper on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) contamination.
3. European Commission, Health and Consumer Protection Directorate-General, Scientific Committee on Food, 2002. Opinion of the scientific committee on food on the risk to human health of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons –occurrence in food, SCF/CS/CNTM/PAH/29.
4. Moret, S., Conte, L.S. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in edible fats and oils: occurrence and analytical methods. *J. Chromatography B* 2000 ; 882: 245-253.
5. Naccari, C., Cristani, M., Giofrè, F., Siracusa, L., Ferrante, M., Trombetta, D. PAHs concentration in heat-treated milk samples. *Food Research International* 2011; 44: 716-724.
6. Naccari, C., Cristani, M., Licata, P., Giofrè, F., Trombetta, D. Levels of Benzo(a)pyrene and Benzo(a)anthracene in “Provola” cheese from Calabria. *Journal of Food Additives and Contaminants* 2008; 1(1): 78-84.
7. Huderson A.C., Myers J.N., Niaz M.S., Washington M.K., Ramesh A. Chemoprevention of benzo(a)pyrene-induced colon polyps in ApcMin mice by resveratrol. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry* 2013; 24(4): 713–724.
8. Kazerouni N, Sinha R, Hsu C-H, Greenberg A, Rothman N. Analysis of 200 food items for benzo(a)pyrene and estimation of its intake in an epidemiologic study. *Food Chemical Toxicology* 2001; 39: 423–436.
9. Ramesh A, Walker SA, Hood DB, Guillen MD, Schneider K, Weyand EH. Bioavailability and risk assessment of orally ingested polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. *International Journal of Toxicology* 2004; 23: 301– 333.
10. Greenwald, P., Clifford, C.K., Milner, J.A. Diet and cancer prevention. *European Journal of Cancer* 2001; 37: 948–965
11. Terry, P., Terry, J. B., Wolk, A. Fruit and vegetable consumption in the prevention of cancer: An update. *Journal Internal Medicine* 2001; 250: 280–290.
12. Halliwell, B. Dietary polyphenols: good, bad or indifferent for your health. *Cardiovascular Research* 2007; 73: 341-347.
13. Ebert, B., Seidel, A., Lampen, A. Phytochemicals induce breast cancer resistance protein in Caco-2 cells and enhance the transport of benzo(a)pyrene-3-sulfate. *Toxicology Science* 2007; 96(2): 227–236.
14. Yang, C.S., Landau, J.M., Huang, M.T., Newmark, H. L. Inhibition of carcinogenesis by dietary polyphenolic compounds. *Annual Review of Nutrition* 2001; 21: 381–389.
15. Al-Shalmani, S., Suri, S., Hughes, D.A., Kroon, P., Needs, P., Taylor, M., Tribolo, S., Wilson, V.G. Quercetin and its principal metabolites, but not myricetin, oppose lipopolysaccharide-induced hyporesponsiveness of the porcine isolated coronary artery. *British Journal of Pharmacology* 2011; 162: 1485-1497.
16. Li Y, Yao J, Han C, Yang J, Chaudhry MT, Wang S, Liu H, Yin Y. Quercetin, Inflammation and Immunity. *Nutrients* 2016; 8(3), E167.
17. Kawabata K, Mukai R, Ishisaka A. Quercetin and related polyphenols: new insights and implications for their bioactivity and bioavailability. *Food Function* 2015; 6(5): 1399-1417.
18. Boots, A.W., Haenen, G.R., Bast, A. Health effects of quercetin: from antioxidant and nutraceutical. *European Journal of Pharmacology* 2008; 585: 325337.

19. Meinel, W., Ebert, B., Glatt H., Lampen, A. Sulfotransferase forms expressed in human intestinal Caco-2 and TC7 cells at varying stages of differentiation and role in benzo(a)pyrene metabolism. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition* 2008; 36: 276–283.
20. Hidalgo, I.J., Raub, T.J., Borchardt, R.T. Characterization of the human colon carcinoma cell line (Caco-2) as a model system for intestinal epithelial permeability. *Gastroenterology* 1989; 96: 736–749.
21. Chantret, I., Rodolosse, A., Barbat, A., Dussaulx, E., Brot-Laroche, E., Zweibaum, A., Rousset, M. Differential expression of sucrase-isomaltase in clones isolated from early and late passages of the cell line Caco-2: evidence for glucose-dependent negative regulation. *Journal of Cell Science* 1994; 107: 213225.
22. Barrington, R., Williamson, G., Bennett, R., Davis, B.D., Brodbelt, J.S., Kroon, P.A. Absorption, conjugation and efflux of the flavonoids, kaempferol and galangin, using the intestinal CACO-2/TC7 cell model. *Journal of Functional Foods* 2009; 1(1): 74–87.
23. Kuhnle, G., Spencer, J.P., Schroeter, H., Shenoy, B., Debnam, E.S., Srail, S.K., Rice-Evans, C., Hahn, U. Epicatechin and catechin are O-methylated and glucuronidated in the small intestine. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Research Communication* 2000; 277: 507–51.
24. Day, A.J., Cañada, F.J., Díaz, J.C., Kroon, P.A., McLauchlan, R., Faulds, C.B., Plumb, G.W., Morgan, M.R.A., Williamson, G. Dietary flavonoid and isoflavone glycosides are hydrolysed by the lactase site of lactase phlorizin hydrolase. *FEBS Letters* 2000; 468: 166–170.
25. Nemeth, K., Plumb, G.W., Berrin, J., Juge, N., Jacob, R., Naim, H.Y., Williamson, G., Swallow, D.M., Kroon, P.A. Deglycosylation by small intestinal epithelial cell β -glucosidase is a critical step in the absorption and metabolism of dietary flavonoid glycosides in humans. *European Journal Nutrition* 2003; 42: 29–42.
26. Manach, C., Scalbert, A., Morand, C., Remesy, C., Jimenez, L. Polyphenols: food sources and bioavailability. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 2004, 79: 727–747.
27. Day, A.J., Mellon, F., Barron, D., Sarrazin, G., Morgan, M.R.A., Williamson, G. Human metabolism of dietary flavonoids: Identification of plasma metabolites of quercetin. *Free Radical Research* 2001; 35: 941–952.
28. Walle, T., Otake, Y., Walle, U.K., Wilson, F.A. Quercetin Glucosides Are Completely Hydrolyzed in Ileostomy Patients before Absorption. *Journal of Nutrition* 2000; 130: 2658–2661.
29. Buesen, R., Mock, M., Nau, H., Seidel, A., Jacob, J., Lampen, A. Human intestinal Caco-2 cells display active transport of benzo(a)pyrene metabolites. *Chem. Bio Interact* 2003; 142: 201–221.
30. Buesen, R., Mock, M., Seidel, A., Jacob, J., Lampen, A. Interaction between Metabolism and Transport of Benzo(a)pyrene and Its Metabolites in Enterocytes. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology* 2002; 183: 168–178.
31. Vasiluk, L., Pinto, L.J., Tsang, W.S., Gobas, F.A., Eickhoff, C., Moore, M.M. The uptake and metabolism of benzo(a)pyrene from a sample food substrate in an in vitro model of digestion. *Food Chemical Toxicology*, 2008; 46(2): 610–8.
32. Ebert, B., Seidel, A., Lampen, A. Identification of BCRP as transporter of benzo(a)pyrene conjugates metabolically formed in Caco-2 cells and its induction by Ah-receptor agonists. *Carcinogenesis* 2005; 26: 1754–1763.
33. Lampen, A., Ebert, B., Stumkat, L., Jacob, J., Seidel, A. Induction of gene expression of xenobiotic metabolism enzymes and ABC-transport proteins by PAH and a reconstituted PAH mixture in human Caco-2 cells. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* 2004; 1681: 38–46.
34. Sergent, T., Ribonnet, L., Kolosova, A., Garsou, S., Schaut, A., De Saeger, S., Van Peteghem, C., Larondelle, Y., Pussemier, L., Schneider, Y.J. Molecular and cellular effects of food contaminants and secondary plant components and their plausible interactions at the intestinal level. *Food Chemical Toxicology* 2008; 46: 813–841.
35. Niestroy, J., Barbara, A., Herbst, K., Rode, S., van Liempt, M., Roos, P.H. Single and concerted effects of benzo(a)pyrene and flavonoids on the AhR and Nrf2-pathway in the human colon carcinoma cell line Caco-2. *Toxicology In Vitro* 2011.; 25(3): 671–83.
36. Das, M., Bickers, D.R., Mukhtar, H. Effect of ellagic acid on hepatic and pulmonary xenobiotic metabolism in mice: studies on the mechanism of its anticarcinogenic action. *Carcinogenesis* 1985; 6(10): 1409–13.
37. Uhl, M., Ecker, S., Kassie, F., Lhoste, E. Chakraborty, A., Mohn, G., Knasmüller, S. Effect of chrysin, a flavonoid compound, on the mutagenic activity of 2-amino-1-methyl-6-phenylimidazo[4,5-b]pyridine (PhIP) and benzo(a)pyrene (B(a)P) in bacterial and human hepatoma (HepG2) cells. *Archives of Toxicology* 2003; 77(8): 477–84.
38. Bothe, A., Gassmann, K., Götz, C., Fritsche, E., Abel, J., Haarmann-Stemmann, T. Epigallocatechin-3-gallate does not affect the activity of enzymes involved in metabolic activation and cellular excretion of benzo(a)pyrene in human colon carcinoma cells. *Toxicology Letters* 2011; 203: 258–264.
39. Needs P, Kroon P. Convenient synthesis of metabolically important glucuronides and sulfates. *Tetrahedron* 2006; 62: 6862–6868.
40. Soler, A., Romero, M.P., Macià, A., Saha, S., Furniss, C.S.M., Kroon, P.A., Motilva, M.J. Digestion stability and evaluation of the metabolism and transport of olive oil phenols in the human small-intestinal epithelial Caco-2/TC7 cell line. *Food Chemistry* 2009; 61: 143–149.
41. Nair P, Malhotra A, Dhawan DK. Curcumin and quercetin trigger apoptosis during benzo(a)pyrene-

- induced lung carcinogenesis. *Molecular Cellular Biochemistry* 2015; 400(1-2): 5156.
42. Wu TC, Huang SY, Chan ST, Liao JW, Yeh SL. Combination of β -carotene and quercetin against benzo(a)pyrene-induced proinflammatory reaction accompanied by the regulation of antioxidant enzyme activity and NF- κ B translocation in Mongolian gerbils. *European Journal of Nutrition* 2015; 54(3): 397-406.
43. Chang YZ, Lin HC, Chan ST, Yeh SL. Effects of quercetin metabolites on the enhancing effect of β carotene on DNA damage and cytochrome P1A1/2 expression in benzo(a)pyrene-exposed A549 cells. *Food Chemistry* 2012; 133(2): 445-450.
44. Liu Y, Wu YM, Zhang PY. Protective effects of curcumin and quercetin during benzo(a)pyrene induced lung carcinogenesis in mice. *European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Science*, 2015; 19(9):1736-1743.
45. Krishnan R1, Raghunathan R, Maru GB. Effect of polymeric black tea polyphenols on benzo(a)pyrene [B(a)P]-induced cytochrome P4501A1 and 1A2 in mice. *Xenobiotica* 2005; 35(7): 671-82.
46. Wen X. and Walle T. Preferential induction of CYP1B1 by benzo(a)pyrene in human oral epithelial cells: impact on DNA adduct formation and prevention by polyphenols. *Carcinogenesis* 2005; 26 (10): 1774-1781.
47. Robaszekiewicz A, Balcerczyk A, Bartosz G. Antioxidative and prooxidative effects of quercetin on A549 cells. *Cell Biology International* 2007; 31(10):1245-50.
48. Chiarugi P , Fiaschi T. Redox signalling in anchorage-dependent cell growth. *Cellular Signalling* 2007; 19(4). 672-682.
49. Turpaev, K.T. Reactive oxygen species and regulation of gene expression. *Biochemistry (Mosc)*. 2002; 67(3): 281-92.
50. Leslie, E.M., Mao, Q., Oleschuk, C.J., Deeley, R.G., Cole, S.P. Modulation of multidrug resistance protein 1 (MRP1/ABCC1) transport and atpase activities by interaction with dietary flavonoids. *Molecular Pharmacology* 2001; 59(5): 1171-80.
51. Barrington, R.D., Needs, P.W., Williamson, G., Kroon, P.A. MK571 inhibits phase-2 conjugation of flavonols by Caco-2/TC7 cells but does not specifically inhibit their apical efflux. *Biochemical Pharmacology* 2015; 95: 193–200.